

THE ROLE OF STANDARDS DEVELOPING ORGANISATIONS (SDO) IN THE ACHIEVEMENT OF SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY FOR DPP

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Abstract	This document provides recommendations to standards developing organisations (SDOs) on how these can support the further digitalisation of industry through the creation of interoperable data and vocabularies. It also discusses the cost and benefits of interoperable data and how to lift the barriers to its further adoption.
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47	Green Electronics Council	GEC	US
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Data becomes *'interoperable'* when it can be received and reused unambiguously and easily by any party, including by any information system. Data interoperability is therefore a must for efficient data exchanges in global and open data sharing ecosystems. Digital Product Passports (DPP) are a notable example of a global, open data sharing ecosystem, where data is exchanged in multiple stakeholder contexts (B2B, B2C, B2G, etc.)

For data to become fully interoperable, common formats and structure are required, but the meaning of the data must also be defined explicitly. This is done by applying the principles of semantic interoperability and through the use of shared **vocabularies**. These last are, fundamentally, agreements on how to name things. However, because vocabularies are a form of 'digital commons', their creation and adoption come with an upfront cost. This means that many organisations don't necessarily see the value of adopting semantic interoperability, with its upfront costs but long-term benefits, versus the status quo of sharing data with limited interoperability (no upfront costs, but costly solutions often needed later to manage inconsistencies and semantic conflicts or to perform manual data transformations to the requested target format.)

Standardisation Developing Organisations (SDOs) have a long experience of harnessing collective efforts towards common objectives that can only be achieved through cooperation. SDOs therefore play a key role in reducing the cost of vocabulary creation and in supporting industry's transition towards exchanges of interoperable data.

In the context of increasing reliance on the exchange of machine-readable data, of which the Digital Product Passport (DPP) is an example, this paper discusses the ingredients for interoperable data and presents the five different 'levels' of semantic interoperability currently being considered for DPPs. It then discusses the role that SDOs should continue to play in the future to support the greater development of interoperable data. Semantic interoperability is a real opportunity for SDOs to develop new support services to be closer to the needs of their stakeholders.

1 INTRODUCTION: WHAT IS INTEROPERABLE DATA?

Data becomes ‘*interoperable*’ when it can be received and reused unambiguously and easily by any party, including by any information system. Data interoperability is therefore a must for efficient data exchanges in multi-stakeholder contexts (e.g. B2B, B2G, etc.) Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs) play a key role in supporting the creation of interoperable data. The reason for this is that data interoperability relies heavily on the use of shared **vocabularies**, a form of ‘digital commons’, the development of which strongly benefits from collective efforts. Standardisation bodies have a long experience of harnessing collective efforts towards common objectives that can only be achieved through cooperation.

In the context of increasing reliance on the exchange of machine-readable data, of which the Digital Product Passport (DPP) is an example, this paper discusses the ingredients for interoperable data and the role that SDOs should continue to play in the future to support its greater development.

1.1 WHAT IS SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY?

One of the main ingredients for interoperable data is ‘semantic interoperability’. According to the [European Commission](#), “semantic interoperability ensures that the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties”. In other words, the meaning of the exchanged data remains intact and is understood by all parties (which can be humans or machines).

The preservation of meaning in information exchange is however not the only objective of semantic interoperability according to Wikipedia¹ which also stresses other capabilities required by information systems:

“Semantic interoperability is the ability of computer systems to exchange data with unambiguous, shared meaning. Semantic interoperability is a requirement to enable machine computable logic, inferencing, knowledge discovery, and data federation between information systems. Semantic interoperability is therefore concerned not just with the packaging of data (syntax), but the simultaneous transmission of the meaning with the data (semantics). This is accomplished by adding data about the data (metadata), linking each data element to a controlled, shared vocabulary. The meaning of the data is transmitted with the data itself, in one self-describing “information package” that is independent of any information system. It is this shared vocabulary, and its associated links to an ontology, which provides the foundation and capability of machine interpretation, inference, and logic.”

According to the European Commission’s [Semantic Interoperability Courses](#), semantic interoperability is achieved when social agreements are reached on **vocabularies**, i.e. common specifications for naming things, and on structural metadata². This last provides structural context for interpreting data by describing how data is organized and structured. Structural metadata typically consists of reference data, a small set of values that are usually used to impose consistent classification, and a **data model**.

A data model is a collection of entities, their properties, and the relationships among them, designed to represent a domain, concept, or real-world entity. A data model contains:

- **Classes:** the different types of things that exist in the data, usually organized in a class hierarchy.
- **Relationships (or object properties):** properties that connect two classes, usually organized in a property hierarchy.
- **Attributes (or data properties):** characteristics that define an individual class and are relationships between a class and a literal.

Vocabularies, i.e. names for things and their associated definitions ideally expressed in multiple languages, are required for each of the above classes and properties. Once defined, these vocabularies (i.e. the term/definition pairs) can be stored in an **ontology**. In practice, two main approaches are used to represent such knowledge structures. A first approach relies on **dictionary-based ontology standards**, where concepts and properties are organized within structured terminology systems or reference data libraries. Examples include EN ISO 12006, EN ISO 23386, and IEC 61360. A second approach relies on **ontology representation languages**. These languages allow concepts, relationships, and any constraints that are applicable to these concepts and properties to be expressed using formal logic. In this case, knowledge is represented in a machine-interpretable language that enables automated reasoning, such as consistency checking or the inference of implicit knowledge. The Web

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semantic_interoperability (accessed March 8, 2026)

²According to ISO/IEC 11179-1, metadata is data that defines and describes other data.

Ontology Language (OWL) is the most widely used standard for this purpose.

1.2 REQUIREMENTS FOR VOCABULARIES

As stated above, to reach the primary objective of semantic interoperability, which is the preservation of meaning in data exchanges, **vocabularies** are needed. Data understanding is facilitated when access to these vocabularies is made simple and easy. For this reason, vocabularies should respect **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

- Findable: Vocabularies should be resolvable using globally unique identifiers (Web URIs). For example, the term 'Claim' is defined in the UNTP namespace: <https://vocabulary.uncefact.org/untp/Claim>
- Accessible: Access to vocabularies should be timeless, persistent, and free. Persistence requires that the chosen namespace (<https://vocabulary.uncefact.org/untp> in the above example) must be VERY reliable and stable.
- Interoperable: Similarly to data, it should be easy to combine vocabularies from multiple sources. Furthermore, vocabularies should be made available in multiple serialisations.
- Reusable: Because they are a 'digital commons', vocabularies should be designed to be easily reused by others and provided with correspondingly appropriate licencing.

1.3 SEMANTIC CONFLICTS IN DATA INTEGRATION

When integrating data originating from heterogeneous systems, several types of inconsistencies may appear. Some of these issues arise directly at the level of the **data values** themselves. Differences in representation formats, measurement units, or encoding conventions are common examples. Other difficulties emerge at the level of the **data schema** used to organize information. Conflicts on schema level are characterized by differences in logical structures or inconsistencies in metadata. Such divergences make aligning the datasets difficult, even though they describe similar information. Beyond representational and structural issues, **meaning discrepancies** may occur. For example, the same term may be used across domains to refer to distinct concepts or different terms can be used to designate the same notion. Finally, semantic conflicts also arise from **implicit interpretations** embedded in local information systems such as differences in measurement scope, lifecycle stages, or regulatory definitions. These semantic mismatches are harder to detect and are not always visible in the data or the schema thus making the exchanged information unusable or misunderstood when exchanged across organizational or sectoral boundaries.

1.4 THE COST OF SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY

A data economy, in which data becomes a monetizable asset, requires data that can circulate and be reused across systems and organizations, including B2B, B2C and regulatory contexts. For example, vocabularies used for the description of a textile's fibre composition, including the proportion of cotton, polyester, wool, or recycled fibres, can be used to communicate in B2B contexts with downstream partners such as brands, retailers, recyclers, and sorting operators. In a B2C context, the same semantic artifacts can be used to present clear material composition information to consumers through a product page or Digital Product Passport. In a regulatory context, those same artifacts can also support compliance checks and reporting obligations related to textile labelling, substantiated sustainability claims, or recycled content declarations. This illustrates how a single semantically defined data element can be reused across commercial, consumer-facing, and regulatory contexts without redefining its meaning each time. However, such reuse is only possible when data is interoperable, i.e. its meaning is explicitly defined so that the received data is correctly interpreted.

Unfortunately, achieving interoperability requires significant investments in creating and adopting shared semantic resources. This leads to a classic **"chicken-and-egg"** situation: the value of interoperable data cannot be realized without prior investments in interoperability, yet such investments are difficult to justify before clear economic benefits materialize from the reuse of data (for the data creator) and the reduction of semantic conflicts (for the data integrator).

One of the main reasons semantic interoperability remains difficult to achieve is the **cost of designing and maintaining shared vocabularies**. Developing publicly accessible vocabularies requires substantial upfront investments in domain expertise, modelling, governance, and long-term maintenance. These costs explain why

some vocabularies remain proprietary or accessible only through paiement schemes, thereby limiting their adoption to relatively closed business ecosystems. In closed ecosystems, data exchange can only occur between actors that already have a pre-existing business relationship. These economic considerations explain both the importance of reusing existing vocabularies whenever possible and the central role of standard development organizations (SDOs) in creating and maintaining shared semantic resources, with several examples provided in Section 3.1.

Even when suitable vocabularies exist, another important cost arises from **their adoption by stakeholders**. Each organization operates its own information systems typically built around locally defined data structures and terminology whose meanings are often implicit and context-dependent. Making such data interoperable requires a process that can be described as the *semantification of data*: local data structures must be mapped to shared vocabularies before being exported or exchanged. Implementing and maintaining these mappings requires dedicated tools and expertise and therefore represents a significant investment for organizations.

1.5 THE ECONOMIC BENEFITS OF SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY

For the reasons mentioned above, stakeholders require a clear **return on investment (ROI)** before adopting shared vocabularies and other semantic interoperability concepts. The economic value of semantic interoperability is most evident in “generate once, use many times” scenarios, where the same data can be frequently reused. In the context of Digital Product Passports (DPPs), such scenarios may include:

- A supplier sharing product data (e.g., master data, certificates, traceability information) with multiple customers.
- A DPP supporting compliance with multiple regulatory or administrative requirements.
- Organizations combining data from multiple internal and external sources for analytics or operational purposes (i.e. data fusion).

Once the cost of producing interoperable data has been incurred, organizations benefit from the ability to reuse the data across multiple regulatory, commercial, or operational contexts. The absence of interoperable data means that organizations often incur significant costs later in the form of data integration projects, data cleaning efforts, and tedious and error-prone ad hoc mappings between incompatible systems. Worse, they become captive to third-party data platforms that centralize data to facilitate sharing. Semantic interoperability offers a means to avoid the risk of such centralization.

Specifically to the DPP context, semantic interoperability also offers automatic and demonstrable digital conformity by binding data to the vocabularies which provide legal authority for conformity.

1.6 WHY SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY IS MANDATORY FOR DPP

In [Hbeich et al. \(2025\)](#), seven reasons are given to explain why semantic interoperability is a crucial requirement for DPPs. Indeed, there is a need to:

- Facilitate data reuse across circular ecosystems
- Facilitate data retention over supply-chains
- Facilitate data reuse across sectors
- Ensure interoperability between different international DPP systems
- Facilitate the exchange and reuse of verifiable credentials of all types, including company identity credentials
- Facilitate the reuse of DPP data by public administrations for reporting burden reduction
- Build upon all semantics-related standardisation efforts

From these examples, we see that DPPs are embedded in global-scale data ecosystems. These ecosystems are **open** in the sense that opportunities for data reuse cannot be defined a priori. Semantic interoperability becomes a key technical condition for enabling data to flow and be reused across these **open data ecosystems**.

2 LEVELS OF SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY FOR DPP

Today, most DPP-related **platform-based** initiatives ignore the need for semantic interoperability. Here, typically, a platform operator imposes terms, meanings and formats to all of their clients and assume the responsibility of sharing the provided data with other connected clients. The platform operator obviously has no interest in making data interoperable as this would mean allowing data to leave their platform. This approach will not be further discussed here.

In this section, we show that there are **five levels** of semantic interoperability currently being considered for DPP. These 'levels' are defined according to the capabilities offered by the approach and are ordered by least to most capable. The levels differ in the manner in which semantic information can be partially decoupled or embedded into the exchanged payload. While the approaches are listed according to a maturity ladder, specific approaches may be fit-for-purpose depending on the use case and required capabilities. Finally, all five approaches create interoperability because the meaning of the data is transmitted with the data itself.

2.1 TEMPLATE-BASED SEMANTICS

The first semantification method uses a decoupled template-based approach. In this approach, the exchanged payload contains structured data but does not include the semantic description (i.e. meaning and associated metadata) of each data element. These are defined in an externally stored template reference document which can be found thanks to a reference to this template document in the data payload. This reference can be in the form of a web link or consist of a template identifier generated by a template repository. If the location of the template repository is not also contained in the data, then the level of semantic interoperability achieved is lowered.

This approach corresponds to the compressed JSON serialization format proposed in prEN 18223 for the EU DPP where the external semantic repository and data structures are referenced using attributes such as *contentSpecificationIds* and *SchemaVersion*. Then, the structured data value's key name is used as JSON key together with its value, for instance,

```
{
  "Poper": 2.5
}
```

Metadata associated with the data element, such as meaning, the value data type and units, are defined in the referenced template document. Consequently, correctly interpreting the exchanged data depends on the consistency between the key names used in the payload and the definitions defined in the template.

Data templates essentially correspond to standardised, use-case-oriented data blocks. They are often considered of great value in industry and can indeed be very useful. But, because they must be defined *a priori* and are difficult to change *a posteriori*, they unfortunately lack flexibility and offer limited capabilities. They can also become a source of confusion as some data elements may be defined in several templates, making it difficult to identify the single-source of truth.

Templates also rely on a centralized template repository operator who may or may not impose constraints related to template creation, e.g. [IDTA](#). The template-based approach enables a very compact representation for the data.

2.2 EMBEDDED SEMANTIC REFERENCES

The second semantification method depends on the explicit inclusion of semantic references for each data element in the exchanged payload. In the example below, this is done using the *dictionaryReference* attribute, where the provided reference corresponds to an IRDI as defined for the **operating pressure (Poper)** property in the IEC 61360-4 reference dictionary. Additional metadata provides information about the data element's type, the data type of its value, and the value itself.

```
{
  "elementId": "Poper",
  "objectType": "SingleValuedDataElement",
  "dictionaryReference": "0112/2///61360_4#AAE866#001",
  "value": 2.5
}
```

```
"valueDataType": "LEVEL(MIN,MAX) OF REAL_MEASURE_TYPE",  
"value": 2.5  
}
```

The datatype shown here corresponds to the datatype definition used in the IEC 61360 Common Data Dictionary associated with the referenced IRDI. The level of semantic interoperability achieved here remains limited as the meaning of the *dictionaryReference* field also needs to be communicated to the data receiver who must then perform manual look-ups. This example is similar to the expanded JSON serialisation format from prEN 18223 for the EU DPP. The representation is less compact but more explicit.

2.3 RESOLVABLE VOCABULARIES

The third semantification method depends on globally unique web resolvable vocabularies, which has the simultaneous benefit of providing globally unique identifiers for terms (with no need to find other means to communicate the location of the used dictionary) and of allowing the meaning and other metadata of a term to be accessed directly through its reference. Dereferenceable vocabularies improve the portability of data across different systems. Indeed, because each term is globally unique, it becomes much easier to combine data from different sources. In this example, the term “Poper” is made globally unique thanks to the “dictionary1.eu” domain. This example also corresponds to the expanded JSON serialisation format from prEN 18223 for the EU DPP.

```
{  
  "elementId": "Poper",  
  "objectType": "SingleValuedDataElement",  
  "dictionaryReference": "https://dictionary1.eu/Poper",  
  "valueDataType": "xsd:float",  
  "value": 2.5  
}
```

2.4 RESOLVABLE VOCABULARIES - COMPACT VERSION

A popular, but more compact, alternative approach to the previous one is to use JSON-LD, in which each term is linked to a resolvable, globally unique IRI via an “@context” definition. For example, a data element might look like this:

```
{  
  "@context": "https://dictionary1.eu",  
  "Poper": 2.5  
}
```

The result is a serialisation format similar to the compressed JSON serialization format proposed in prEN 18223 for the EU DPP. The level of compactness achieved is similar to the template-based approach described above. To leverage existing vocabularies, the JSON-LD “@context” can be used to combine vocabularies from several sources with no ambiguity, like this:

```
{  
  "@context": {  
    "ex": "https://dictionary1.eu/",  
    "schema": "https://schema.org/"  
  },  
  "ex:Poper": 2.5,  
  "schema:unitCode": "BAR"  
}
```

This approach also makes it possible to transform the exchanged data directly into an RDF graph. JSON-LD is the serialisation format used by the UNTP DPP, currently being standardised by UN/CEFACT.

2.5 ONTOLOGY-BASED INTEROPERABILITY

Similarly to the fourth approach, the fifth approach relies on globally unique, web resolvable vocabularies which, now, are embedded into an ontology. The ontology itself is not transmitted with the data which thus remains

identical to the example in section 2.4. If needed, the one (or more) used ontology can be retrieved by following the vocabulary links. Most ontologies are defined using an **ontology representation language** such as OWL. Such computer languages allow concepts, relationships, and, most importantly, constraints that are applicable to these concepts and properties to be expressed using formal logic. Through this formalization, it also becomes possible to represent not only the structure of the data but also the semantics associated with the different elements of the model, i.e., the model of the model, a.k.a. the meta-model. Globally unique web resolvable vocabularies are also used for this meta-modelling purpose (e.g. [RDF Schema](#)). The goal is to leave as little implicit knowledge as possible in the data (as it is never certain what *a priori* knowledge the data receiver will have about the data) by making it as explicit as possible.

When data is modelled using a formal knowledge representation language, additional capabilities become possible. For example, automatic verification of constraints such as domain validity (i.e. applicability of a property to a class), data value ranges, axioms or logical restrictions can be performed to validate the consistency of the complete domain model. The same tools can support the detection of inconsistencies or rule violations in the data itself. Moreover, formal ontologies facilitate the automatic alignment of vocabularies originating from different systems and therefore facilitate the integration of data and knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hereby avoiding tedious and error-prone mapping tasks. *Alignment* means determining that two terms are synonyms, or that one is a specialisation or generalisation of another. Finally, formal ontologies make it possible to exploit trustworthy logical reasoning mechanisms to infer new knowledge from existing datasets and also build higher-quality LLM-based functionalities for the further processing and interrogation of data.

Ontology-based interoperability is both the name and focus of the upcoming [ISO 23726](#) for the management of the life cycle phases of industrial assets and processes.

3 THE ROLE OF SDOS IN THE ACHIEVEMENT OF SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY FOR DPP

Public administrations, such as the [European Commission's Publication Office](#), have a long history of **creating, maintaining and hosting** globally unique, web resolvable vocabularies for their needs. In the case of the EU Publication Office, one of the needs is the improvement of document referencing consistency with all European and Member State institutions. Scientific institutions, e.g. the [British Oceanographic Data Centre](#), just to name one, also have a long history of creating, maintaining and hosting such vocabularies.

However, because developing high-quality, publicly accessible, persistent vocabularies for the needs of businesses requires industry **cooperation and substantial investments** in domain expertise, modelling, governance, and long-term maintenance, it is less easy for industry to do the same. This is why standards developing organisations (SDOs) have a significant role to play in this area.

3.1 EXAMPLES OF SDOS INVOLVEMENT IN THE DESIGN OF VOCABULARIES

Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) have a long-standing track-record of creating, maintaining and governing shared vocabularies that support semantic interoperability. A few examples from major SDO initiatives are provided below.

3.1.1 EXAMPLES FROM THE WORLD WIDE WEB CONSORTIUM (W3C)

The W3C is the standardisation body responsible for the creation of the core Semantic Web standards and the Resource Description Framework (RDF), a data model, in which vocabularies play a fundamental role to express semantics. These vocabularies can be used either to describe the structure of the data (e.g., RDF, RDFS, OWL) or to represent domain-specific knowledge. These include terms (classes and properties) to describe RDF concepts such as resources, types, and properties defined in the RDF vocabulary, knowledge modelling concepts ([RDFS](#) and [SKOS](#)), and ontology-related concepts ([OWL](#)). The W3C is also responsible for defining [XML Schema](#) vocabularies, used in particular for datatypes in RDF, and many others ([list](#)). For example, [DCAT](#) is an RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs published on the Web. The [ODRL](#) vocabularies describe the terms used by the ODRL language which can be used to represent statements about the usage of content and services. More recently, data models and associated vocabularies have been created for aspects related to [Verifiable Credentials](#).

3.1.2 EXAMPLE FROM THE EUROPEAN TELECOMMUNICATIONS STANDARDS INSTITUTE (ETSI)

The Smart Applications REFerence ontology ([SAREF](#)) by ETSI's [TC DATA](#) is a reference ontology for the Internet of Things domain whose goal is to support interoperability among smart appliances produced by different manufacturers and operating under heterogeneous communication protocols. SAREF provides a semantic layer intended to enable information originating from different protocols and platforms to be translated and understood consistently across systems [Daniele et al. \(2018\)](#). The SAREF ontology defines a set of core concepts that are common across multiple IoT domains. Then, domain-specific extensions capture the semantics required in different application areas, e.g. energy, buildings, environment, smart cities, industry and manufacturing, agriculture, automotive, health, and wearables. In this way, SAREF can be seen as a semantic hub that connects heterogeneous vertical domains while preserving a shared conceptual core [Lefrançois \(2023\)](#).

3.1.3 EXAMPLE FROM ISO/IEC

The [ISO/IEC 21838-2:2021](#) standard specifies the BFO (Basic Formal Ontology). BFO is a domain-neutral, top-level ontology that aims to provide terms representing only highly general categories – such as object, quality, process, spatial and temporal region – which are intended to pertain to all domains of reality. Its goal is to facilitate the semantic interchange of information among heterogeneous information systems, across domains. BFO terms are published using the [BFO vocabularies](#) <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo> namespace.

3.1.4 EXAMPLE FROM ISO

[ISO/TC 184/SC 4 \(Industrial data\)](#) is responsible for a number of standards that aim to help different industrial systems understand and share data. In particular, the more than 20-year-old ISO 15926 set of standards for the representation of process plant life-cycle information, along with the BFO ontology, has influenced the recent development of the [Industrial Data Ontology \(IDO\)](#). The IDO is meant to serve as an upper-level ontology

for industrial data. Its ontology is published under the <http://rds.posccaesar.org/ontology/lis14/ont/core> namespace. The IDO is developed and published in the context of the ISO 23726 set of standards for ontology-based interoperability for the management of the life cycle phases of industrial assets and processes.

3.1.5 EXAMPLE FROM INTERNATIONAL ELECTROTECHNICAL COMMISSION (IEC)

The IEC Common Data Dictionary (CDD, IEC 61360-4) is an IEC-hosted dictionary system that acts as a common repository for data dictionaries for ISO and IEC industrial and electrotechnical related-domains. Domain-specific dictionaries hosted in the CDD provide standardized definitions for components, properties, and related concepts. CDD-hosted data dictionaries may include data from electrotechnical and non-electrotechnical domains. Each element of vocabulary is uniquely identified using an IRDI (International Registration Data Identifier).

3.1.6 EXAMPLES FROM GS1

The EPCIS event data model and ontology were designed to capture and share data describing the life cycle of products as they move over heterogeneous supply-chain systems. This event model is complemented by Core Business Vocabulary (CBV), which provides a controlled set of business terms associated with EPCIS events. CBV constrains the vocabulary used in EPCIS data exchanges by defining values such as business steps, dispositions, and event types. The EPCIS and CBV vocabularies are made available under the <https://ref.gs1.org/epcis> and <https://ref.gs1.org/cbv/> namespaces, respectively.

In addition, GS1 provides the GS1 Web Vocabulary, which expresses terms defined in various GS1 standards and data systems following Linked Data principles. This vocabulary extends the popular schema.org vocabularies by introducing classes and properties aligned with GS1 identification keys and product attributes, making it easier for product data to be published and consumed as linked data on the Web. Where relevant, mappings and relationships between this and the Schema.org vocabularies are made explicit.

3.1.7 EXAMPLES FROM UN/CEFACT

The UN/CEFACT, operating under the UNECE, develops standards to support interoperable electronic business and international trade processes. Its semantic artefacts are grounded in the Buy-Ship-Pay Reference Data Model, which captures core business processes. These models are exposed as Linked Data through the UN/CEFACT Web Vocabularies, enabling reuse via web-resolvable identifiers. The vocabularies cover key resources such as UN/LOCODE for location identification and include sustainability-related terms. This approach is further extended by the United Nations Transparency Protocol, which structures traceability and transparency data across value chains and defines a number of vocabularies for DPP. Overall, UN/CEFACT combines conceptual modelling with Linked Data publication, effectively bridging traditional data exchange standards and Semantic Web technologies, and enabling shared, globally identifiable business concepts across systems

3.2 RECOMMENDATIONS TO SDOS

In a recent white paper, AFNOR states that semantic interoperability is a real opportunity for SDOs to develop new support services to be closer to the needs of users AFNOR (2026). In this section, we describe areas of activity where SDOs can indeed create value for their stakeholders, especially in view of the high upfront costs related to semantic interoperability.

3.2.1 PROVIDING SEMANTIC MODELING AND VOCABULARY DESIGN EXPERTISE

To support industry in reaping the economic benefits of semantic interoperability while minimizing its associated costs (as described in Chapter 1), SDOs can offer to pool resources for semantic modeling and vocabulary design expertise. Semantic modeling is a cross-cutting expertise that can be applied across domains. In the context of a domain-specific technical committee, domain experts can work with SDO-provided semantic modeling experts to agree on modeling goals and define the conceptualisation, taking into account the modeling legacy of the technical community. This means that domain experts do not also have to be semantic modeling experts.

A semantic modeling expert is usually familiar with the vocabularies that are most commonly reused in the Semantic Web and Linked Data ecosystem, and whose stability is reflected by their continuous reuse by other vocabularies over time. For example, the LOV repository for open vocabularies (Figure 1) shows reuse relations among widely used open vocabularies. The size of each circle corresponds to the extent to which a vocabulary has been reused. Of course, not all of the cited vocabularies were produced by SDOs, but some of those that were are among the most reused.

Figure 1: SNAPSHOT FROM [HTTPS://LOV.LINKEDDATA.ES/DATASET/LOV/](https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/). MANY OF THE MENTIONED VOCABULARIES ARE MAINTAINED BY SDOs.

Another task that can be performed by the semantic modeling expert is the automatic verification of modeling consistency using reasoners, which can help detect logical inconsistencies and support model revision. By bringing semantic modeling and vocabulary design expertise to industry-led technical committees, SDOs can improve the quality and coherence of modeling and vocabulary/ontology development cycles. Automatic artifact validation is another possible output of the modeling task.

Going forward, one possibility could be to leverage the semantic modeling expertise of research institutions³. While their level of expertise is often high, research institutions are less well positioned when it comes to coordinating long-lasting industrial partnerships, as much of their work with industry partners takes place in relatively short-lived projects. Because SDOs are better placed to build and coordinate long-term industry collaborations, a mutually beneficial collaboration between SDOs and research institutions could be considered. Furthermore, research institutions regularly train computer science PhD graduates and postdoctoral researchers who often specialise in semantic modeling.

3.2.2 EMBRACING DOMAIN MODELING OVERLAPS

All semantic domains overlap to some extent. For example, domains related to functionalities such as logistics, purchasing, manufacturing, maintenance, or certifications, as well as those related to products themselves, necessarily intersect. For instance, an IoT device may belong to both the telecommunications and electrotechnical domains. This means that the same function or device can be modeled differently by different technical committees and be assigned different semantic interpretations by different SDOs. This is a normal process, and it would be neither realistic nor desirable to attempt to avoid the emergence of domain overlaps or even competing domain models. Doing so would require a form of top-down global coordination across all SDOs to assign governance “mandates” to specific semantic domains. In practice, this would likely lead to unproductive conflicts between technical committees, whether across different SDOs or within a single organization.

Rather than viewing semantic overlaps as a problem to be eliminated, this diversity should be understood as a natural consequence of complex ecosystems. This perspective aligns with the reality of many digital environments, where the coexistence of multiple vocabularies, models, and ontologies is inevitable. In such contexts, the objective is not to eliminate diversity, but to manage it through mechanisms such as mappings and alignments, also known

³In Europe, such expertise can be identified, for example, through research teams publishing in venues such as the [European Semantic Web Conference](#).

as semantic mediation⁴.

This situation also creates an opportunity for SDO-provided semantic modeling expertise. Thanks to the use of distinct namespaces (often managed by SDOs), terms defined differently by separate SDOs can be clearly identified and distinguished. When needed, these terms can be related through mapping ontologies expressing correspondences such as equivalence (e.g., `owl:sameAs` or `owl:equivalentClass`), subsumption (e.g., `rdfs:subClassOf`), or other alignment relations, depending on the intended level of semantic compatibility.

3.2.3 SUPPORTING VOCABULARY DIVERSITY

Another opportunity for SDO-provided expertise in vocabulary design consists in providing technical committees with guidance on reusing, well-maintained, well-understood, and most reused existing vocabularies, or combination of vocabularies, that correspond to their needs and design only the required complements. Indeed, thanks to the globally unique nature of each term in a vocabulary, it is possible to combine vocabularies from multiple sources, as long as they are well-documented, maintained over time, and have demonstrated their reuse in multiple applications. Such vocabularies are often aligned with FAIR principles and are embedded in ontologies with well-defined axioms. Again, the semantic modeling expertise provided by the SDO can leverage automatic consistency verification using reasoners to help detect logical inconsistencies and support model refinement.

Thus, it is not excluded that an SDO might reuse a term already defined by another SDO (using their namespace) and mix it with new terms defined using the first SDO's namespace. Depending on the relation to the initial specification, this can be called profiling, regionalisation or extensions. Semantic interoperability is strengthened when the world's best, i.e. most useful and most stable, vocabularies are reused and extended.

3.2.4 SUPPORTING 'TOP-DOWN' AND 'BOTTOM-UP' SEMANTIC CONVERGENCE

Because SDOs exist to serve the interests of companies, their role is to support business ecosystems in adapting their legacy systems towards greater interoperability. These legacy systems necessarily come with considerable heritage, most likely from bottom-up initiatives that continuously emerge out of necessity. This means that even core concepts (date, time, location, address, etc.) are often modeled or interpreted differently across systems. And until semantic interoperability principles become as ubiquitous as the internet, this will remain inevitable. This of course leads to semantic silos or semantic conflicts as described in Section 1.3.

Again, this is an opportunity for SDO-provided expertise to support business communities in adopting well-defined semantic resources, especially for core concepts. Depending on the interoperability goals of the community, core concepts might correspond to those contained in widely reused vocabularies, or to top-level industrial concepts as modeled in the IDO (see 3.1.4), or even to general top-level entities as modeled in the BFO (see 3.1.3), etc. The idea of 'top-level' or 'core' concepts can itself be refined recursively as a conceptualisation becomes more detailed.

3.2.5 DEVELOPING SEMANTICS-AS-A-SERVICE

In the above-cited white paper by AFNOR, the concept of Semantics-as-a-Service is proposed as a possible new service offering by SDOs. Because industry consortia constantly need to define local extensions to standards to reflect local specialisations and variants, and to avoid the risk of creating new semantic silos, SDOs can support these consortia by providing persistent hosting and maintenance of their locally developed vocabularies. By giving them control over a trusted, SDO-hosted namespace, consortia can define the vocabularies they need within a stable and governed environment. Of course, SDO-provided semantic modeling experts can guide consortia in reusing and extending well-established vocabularies rather than redefining them. The role of SDOs, whether at the ecosystem, sector, regional, national or international level, is to support industry consortia in developing the vocabularies required by their business needs.

One example where Semantics-as-a-Service could be particularly useful is in industrial ecosystems such as those found in European project consortia. These often take advantage of the cooperative nature of such programmes, as well as public funding, to develop vocabularies for innovative use cases. However, such consortia are typically short-lived, which limits the maturity that can be achieved by these vocabularies. As a result, industry partners may remain reluctant to rely on them to build new IT services. SDOs can facilitate the maturation of these vocabularies by offering quality-checking, maintenance support and, most importantly, a trusted and persistent namespace. In this way, SDOs provide the stability required for the industrial use of these vocabularies while leveraging their capacity to coordinate industry partnerships over longer periods.

⁴Processes that establish correspondences between ontologies and enable systems to interpret data across heterogeneous semantic representations, often relying on mapping or alignment ontologies.

3.2.6 SUPPORTING INDUSTRY'S TRANSITION TO INTEROPERABLE DATA

Thanks to their neutral role, SDOs are well positioned to provide training on different semantic modeling approaches, standards and corresponding toolsets. They are also well positioned to support industry in adopting the necessary solutions to enable semantically interoperable data exchanges. Indeed, even when industrial ecosystems agree to share data using common vocabularies or ontologies, additional mechanisms such as mappings, contextualisation, and alignments are still required to ensure that information is correctly interpreted and integrated from and into local IT systems.

3.2.7 SUPPORTING MULTIPLE MODELING APPROACHES AND FRAMEWORKS

Because multiple modeling approaches can be used to represent the same body of knowledge (within the limits of the semantic expressiveness of each approach), an SDO's semantic modeling expertise can be used to develop transformations to adapt knowledge models to the needs of industry communities. These knowledge model transformations can themselves become standards.

A non-exhaustive list of modeling standards for systems engineering is provided in [Modeling Standards](#). This means that industry communities come with legacy knowledge modeling frameworks and need approaches that minimize changes to these legacy, but operational, systems. Therefore, rather than attempting to convince industry to comply with a unified set of standards, SDOs should support business communities regardless of the semantic modeling approach they adopt. Such transformations provide value by enabling interoperability and facilitating the integration of heterogeneous data ecosystems.

4 CONCLUSION

Companies struggle with data interoperability issues on a daily basis. To support industry's shift to interoperable data, solutions to lower the upfront cost of adopting semantic interoperability are needed. Not only do all SDOs have an important role to play in this area but they can benefit from substantial opportunities related to the development of new services. The business opportunity of SDOs to bring semantic modeling expertise and vocabulary design, maintenance and hosting services to industry is huge. SDOs have a central role in the creation of 'digital commons', for the benefit of all.

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